

UK SEPSIS

Practitioner Forum

5th AGM & Conference UKSPF

Tuesday 27th November 2018
at Kingston Hospital

CONFERENCE AGENDA

Time	Subject	Speaker	Position
08:30-09:00	Breakfast / Registration		
09:00-09:20	The legacy of William	Melissa Mead	Mother, Ambassador UK Sepsis Trust
09:20-09:50	National paediatric sepsis six pathway	Dr Jeremy Tong	Consultant Paediatric Intensivist, University Hospitals of Leicester NHS Trust
09:50-10:10	A dedication to Maude	Jason Watkins	Father, BATFA award winning actor
10:10-10:20	Questions to panel		
10:20-10:50	Refreshments and Networking		
10:50-11:20	Sepsis UK	Dr Ron Daniels (BEM)	CEO Global Sepsis Alliance, Founder & CEO UK Sepsis Trust, Consultant Intensivist, Good Hope Hospital
11:20-11:50	Using an evidence based approach to sepsis recognition and management.	Dr Manu Shankar-Hari	NIHR Clinician Scientist, ICU Physician, Sepsis Researcher, Kings College London
11:50-12:20	Management of sepsis – international equalities.	Dr Emmanuel Nsutebu	Consultant infectious diseases, Liverpool Hospital, Chair Sepsis Alliance Africa
11:20-12:30	Questions to panel		
12:30-13:30	Lunch		
13:30-14:30	Annual General Meeting for UKSPF members only.		
14:30-14:55	Understanding antimicrobials for the sepsis patient.	Debbie Lockwood	Advanced Clinical Pharmacist, South Tees Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
14:55-15:20	Sepsis in obstetrics – latest developments.	Dr Audrey Quinn	Professor of Education, Leeds University and Consultant Obstetrician, South Tees Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
15:20-15:30	Questions to panel		
15:30-16:00	Refreshment Break		
16:00-16:20	Sepsis management in Wales – a whole country approach.	Gemma Ellis	Nurse Consultant, Cardiff and Vale University Health Board
16:20-16:50	Introducing lactate measurement into the pre hospital setting.	Rory O'Connor	Northern Ireland Ambulance Service
16:50-17:10	Creating a successful sepsis awareness campaign.	Viola Jackson	Sepsis Specialist Nurse, Leighton Hospital
17:10-17:20	Questions to panel		
17:20-17:30	Close		